

Seasonal, geographical and zonal variations in the quantitative structure of the digestive tubules of mussels, *Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lamark

Variaciones estacionales, geográficas y de zonación en la estructura cuantitativa de los túbulos digestivos de mejillones, *Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lamark

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ABSTRACT

Seasonal, geographical and zonal differences in the mean epithelial thickness (MET) of the digestive tubules of the mussel, *Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lmk., are described and discussed in relation to the reproductive cycle, the degree of pollution, the tide-level and the strength of wave-beating. Four sites from the Coast of Bizkaia were selected to carry out this study. Galea is located in a heavily polluted and exposed area of the Abra estuary (Nerbioi river). Zierbena, also located in the Abra estuary, presents moderate levels of pollution only at certain moments of the tidal cycle. Plentzia (Butroi river) is a site rich in organic particulate materials and poorly exposed. Finally, Lekeitio (Lea river), a clean site, is characterized by a heavy wave-beating. The results indicate that MET is reduced in mussels due to various kinds of environmental stress such as those due to pollution (Zierbena and Galea), long aerial exposures (high tide level), strong wave-beating (Lekeitio), malnutrition or reproductive extra costs related to post-spawning periods (September).

RESUMEN

Se estudian las variaciones estacionales, geográficas y de zonación en el grosor medio epitelial de los túbulos digestivos del mejillón, *Mytilus galloprovincialis* Lmk. Se discute su relación con el ciclo reproductor, el grado de contaminación, el nivel mareal y la fuerza del oleaje. Se seleccionaron cuatro localidades de la costa de Vizcaya para llevar a cabo el estudio: Galea, en una zona muy contaminada y expuesta del estuario del Abra (río Nerbioi); Zierbena, (en el mismo estuario), con niveles medios de contaminación sólo en ciertos momentos del ciclo mareal; Plentzia (río Butroi), rico en materia orgánica y poco expuesto; y Lekeitio (río Lea), no contaminado y muy expuesto. Los resultados indican que el grosor medio epitelial se reduce según diversos parámetros de estrés ambiental tales como la contaminación (Zierbena y Galea), largas exposiciones al aire (en el supralitoral), fuerte oleaje (Lekeitio) y malnutrición o costes reproductivos extraordinarios relacionados con el periodo posterior a la puesta (Septiembre).

KEY WORDS: biomonitoring, pollution, stress response, cellular response, natural stress, bivalve molluscs.

PALABRAS CLAVE: biomonitorización, contaminación, respuesta al estrés, respuesta celular, estrés natural, moluscos bivalvos.

INTRODUCTION

It is well-known that the digestive gland of molluscs is responsive to changes in the environment where these organisms live. Thus, for instance, the structure of the digestive tubules of bivalve molluscs changes in response to a variety of pollutants (LOWE, MOORE AND CLARKE, 1981; BAYNE, WIDDOWS, MOORE, SALKED, WORRAL AND DONKIN, 1982). Natural conditions, which may be very variable in the shore, are also reflected in the morphology of the digestive cells comprising the digestive tubules of intertidal molluscs (THOMPSON, RATCLIFFE AND BAYNE, 1974; THOMPSON, BAYNE, MOORE AND CAREFOOT, 1978; MORTON, 1983; MARIGÓMEZ, SÁEZ, CAJARAVILLE AND ANGULO, 1990; MARIGÓMEZ, SOTO AND ANGULO, 1991; 1992; MARIGÓMEZ, SOTO, ETXEBERRIA AND ANGULO, 1993; PLANA AND LEPENNEC, 1991). Concretely, environmental factors such as salinity, nutrient levels, tide or photoperiod may affect digestive cell structure (ROBINSON, 1983; ROBINSON AND LANGTON, 1980; ROBINSON, PENNINGTON AND LANGTON, 1981; MARIGÓMEZ *ET AL.*, 1990, 1991). Other factors (*i. e.*, reproductive stage and malnutrition) might be also responsible for significant changes in the morphology of the cells comprising the digestive tubules of mussels (CAJARAVILLE, DÍEZ, MARIGÓMEZ AND ANGULO, 1991).

The variations in thickness of the digestive epithelium of bivalves is frequently associated with changes in the environmental quality. Thus, a reduction in the epithelial thickness has been described in oysters collected from polluted sites (COUCH, 1984), in mussels and clams exposed to petroleum derivatives (LOWE *ET AL.*, 1981; AXIAK, GEORGE AND MOORE, 1988; LOWE AND CLARKE, 1989; CAJARAVILLE, MARIGÓMEZ, DÍEZ AND ANGULO, 1992) and in mussels maintained in the laboratory for long time (LOWE *ET AL.*, 1981; CAJARAVILLE *ET AL.*, 1991). The Mean Epithelial Thickness (MET) was first calculated by LOWE *ET AL.* (1981) and then applied by MARIGÓMEZ, ANGULO AND MOYA (1986), RECIO, MARIGÓMEZ, ANGULO AND MOYA

(1988), VEGA, MARIGÓMEZ AND ANGULO (1989), CAJARAVILLE *ET AL.* (1992), MARIGÓMEZ, SOTO AND KORTABITARTE (1996) and MARIGÓMEZ, KORTABITARTE AND DUSSART (1998) to assess the effects of pollutants on the digestive tubules of a variety of molluscs. This parameter has also been used to determine the morphological variability between the digestive tubules of individual mussels in relation to the variability between individuals of the same population (SOTO, AGIRREGOIKOA, PÉREZ AND MARIGÓMEZ, 1990). All the investigations reported above indicate that MET is reduced in response to environmental stressors of different nature.

On the other hand, seasonal trends in the prevalence of atrophic and necrotic tubules (COUCH, 1984; CAJARAVILLE AND ANGULO, 1991; CAJARAVILLE *ET AL.*, 1992) and for neoplastic diseases (FARLEY, OTTO AND REINISCH, 1986) have been found in various bivalve molluscs. These seasonal trends appear related to the end of the reproductive cycle (COUCH, 1984; BROUSSEAU, 1987; PLANA AND LEPENNEC, 1991; MARIGÓMEZ *ET AL.*, 1992) and could influence the quantitative structure of the digestive tubules.

The aims of the present investigation are, therefore, (a) to know whether pollution, nutrient level, and wave-beating strength might affect MET values of mussels, and (b) to determine the influence of the season, as related to different reproductive stages, on the effects of the studied factors on digestive tubule morphology. Furthermore, the presence or not of anomalous morphologies such as necrotic tubules (CAJARAVILLE AND ANGULO, 1991; CAJARAVILLE *ET AL.*, 1991, 1992) will also be investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The following four sites were selected for this investigation in order to analyze different combinations of pollution, nutrient levels and wave-exposure:

Figure 1. Geographical situation of the sampling points.
 Figura 1. Localización geográfica de los lugares de muestreo.

Galea, Zierbena, Plentzia and Lekeitio (Fig. 1, Table I). The sites called Galea and Zierbena are located at the Abra estuary (Bizkaia) and exhibit intermediate to high levels of wave-exposure. Galea, sited in the right side of the estuary, receives directly the impact of

the highly industrialized Nerbioi river. The site called Zierbena, located at the left side of the estuary, receives the pollutant charges from the Nerbioi river during low tide but, however, this rocky shore is covered with clean seawater during high tide. Plentzia is located at

Table I. Summary of the characteristics of the sampling sites and of some parameters of the rivers whose water receives each one (data from several official sources).

Tabla I. Resumen de las características de los puntos de muestreo y de algunos parámetros de los ríos que desembocan en cada uno de ellos (datos tomados de varias fuentes oficiales).

Site	Wave-beating	Pollution level	Rivers features		
			Conductivity ($\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$)	Oxygen (mg/l)	Phosphates ($\mu\text{g.at}/\text{l}$)
Galea	Exposed	High, constant	526.2	10.05	4.84
Zierbena	"	High at low tide level Low at high tide level	"	"	"
Plentzia	Protected	Eutrophic	442.95	9.51	7.79
Lekeitio	Highly exposed	Clean	233.79	12.18	1.09

the left side of the mouth of the Butroi river and may be characterized as a protected site with extremely low wave-exposure. The levels of industrial pollutants are low but, according to VILLATE (1980) the level of particulate organic materials is high. The sampling point referred to as Lekeitio is sited at the San Nikolas island opposite to the Karraspio beach at the mouth of the Lea river. It is a clean site (AGIRREGOIKOA, PÉREZ, MARIGÓMEZ AND ANGULO, 1991) which shows extremely high levels of wave-exposure.

With the aim of investigating the effect of tidal zonation, mussels were collected from all the sites during the periods of wider tidal oscillations (spring tides) in order to properly distinguish high (uppest shore position) and low (lowest shore position) tide zonation level: September 1987, March and late August (1988).

Five mussels were collected from each tide level (2) at each site (4) every season (3). Thus, a total number of 120 mussels were histologically examined. The digestive gland was excised once in the laboratory. After excision, the tissue was fixed in Bouin's liquid, paraffin embedded, sectioned at 8 μm and stained with Masson's trichrome stain. In order to calculate the Mean Epithelial Thickness (MET) of the digestive tubules a planimetric procedure was applied (VEGA ET AL., 1989; SOTO ET AL., 1990). Six tubule sections were randomly selected in each of 4 sections of the digestive gland/gonad complex (60 μm distant one from each other). Thus, 24 tubule sections were drawn per mussel, with the aid of a drawing-tube attachment on a Nikon Optiphot microscope. Section profiles were recorded by means of a Watanabe DT1000 digitizer and the planimetric measures were calculated by an Olivetti M240 personal computer. The signification of the differences in MET values corresponding to different experimental groups were tested using ANOVAs.

The relative volume of the digestive gland comprised of necrotic tubules was calculated in order to establish the rele-

vance of this anomalous condition for each experimental group of mussels. The total surfaces covered by normal and by necrotic tubules in two histological sections of the visceral mass were drawn per individual with the aid of a slide projector. The profiles recorded in this way were digitized in the measuring system previously described and the relative volume density of the digestive gland comprised of necrotic tubules for a pattern mussel representing each group of mussels studied ($n=5$) was thus estimated (Fig. 2). Since the necrotic tubules were not drawn to calculate MET values, the final MET values were attained after correction by considering the relative proportion of necrotic tubules. MET values were corrected after calculation of the section areas covered by non-necrotic tubules (T), remainder tissue (gonad follicles + connective tissue, R), and necrotic tubules (N) - schematically illustrated in Figure 2, as follows:

$$\sum DS = \sum TT - \sum R$$

$$\%N = (\sum NS - \sum DS) \times 100$$

$$\%T = 100 - \%N$$

$$X = (n \times \%N) / \%T, \text{ where } n=24 \text{ for 24 tubule drawings}$$

$$\text{corrected MET} = \sum ET / (24 + X);$$

where: TT, total surface area of the digestive gland section; DS, surface area covered by digestive tubules; NS, surface area covered by necrotic digestive tubules; N, necrotic tubules; T, non-necrotic tubules; R, remainder tissue structures in the digestive gland (mainly connective tissue, some gonad tissue and digestive ducts); % N, percentage of tubules showing the appearance of necrotic tubules; % T, percentage of non-necrotic digestive tubules, MET, mean epithelial thickness in μm ; ET, thickness of the epithelium in a given tubule section (in order to correct MET values we have assumed that ET of necrotic tubules is 0).

Gonadal tissue was found in most mussels collected at any season. In order to consider the reproductive stage associated to different seasons the relative

Figure 2. Procedure used to measure the relative proportion of necrotic tubules in the digestive gland of mussels. Since the necrotic tubules were not drawn to calculate MET values, the final MET values were attained after correction by considering the relative proportion of necrotic tubules. N: necrotic tubules; T: non-necrotic tubules; R: remainder tissue structures in the digestive gland (mainly connective tissue, some gonad tissue and digestive ducts).

Figura 2. Procedimiento empleado para medir la proporción relativa de túbulos necróticos en la glándula digestiva de los mejillones. Ya que los túbulos necróticos se consideraban a la hora de calcular el valor del MET, los valores últimos de este factor se obtenían tras corregirlos considerando la proporción relativa de túbulos necróticos. N: túbulos necróticos; T: túbulos no necróticos; R: restantes tejidos en la glándula digestiva (tejido conectivo, tejido gonadal y conductos digestivos).

presence of this tissue in the visceral mass as well as the relevance of ripe gametes were estimated based on qualitative observations.

RESULTS

Marked differences have been found between the reproductive stages recorded at the three seasons. In September 1987, the gonad tissue is present in few individuals, mainly as scarce degenerating follicles in both males and females. Gonad tissue is more abundant in mussels collected at high tide level. In March 1988, the gonad tissue is very abundant and present some ripe gametes (up to aprox. 50%). No difference between tide levels has been observed. In August 1988, the gonad tissue is not so abundant as in March but almost all follicles are completely

comprised of ripe gametes. In this case, gonad tissue is much more abundant in high tide level than in low tide level.

The occurrence of necrotic tubules is quite a widespread condition in mussels collected in September 1987 (Table II). The maximum peak value for the relative occurrence of this tubule type has been recorded in the low tide level of Zierbena (19% of the digestive gland volume occupied by necrotic tubules). The lowest value found in this season corresponds to the high tide level of Lekeitio (7.7%). However, the relative occurrence of necrotic tubules is of minor relevance in any other season. Thus, the highest value recorded in March corresponds to mussels collected from the high tide level of Galea (2.5%). In August 1988, necrotic tubules were not observed at all in any case.

The results of the planimetric analysis carried out to calculate MET values

Table II. Average relative volume (%) of digestive gland tissue occupied by necrotic tubules in mussels collected at different sites, seasons and tide levels.

Tabla II. Volumen medio relativo (%) de tejido digestivo ocupado por túbulos necróticos en mejillones recogidos en diferentes lugares, estaciones y niveles mareales.

Season	Tide level	Site			
		Galea	Zierbena	Lekeitio	Plentzia
September	low	10.28	18.92	11.76	10.45
	high	14.89	13.04	7.69	10.45
March	low	0.83	0.00	0.83	0.00
	high	2.44	1.64	0.83	0.00
August	low	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	high	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

are summarized in Figure 3 and in Tables III-V.

The lowest MET values have been recorded in September 1987 for the four studied sites (Fig. 3). In this season significant differences between tide levels and between sites have not been found (Table III). However, the interaction term exhibits a significant component of variance. Thus, the MET values recorded in low tide level at Plentzia and Galea are significantly higher than MET values found in any other sample at this season. Site, zonation and their interaction significantly influence MET values in March 1988 and August 1988 (Table III). Thus, MET values are lower at low tide level than at high tide level in Galea in both seasons, while exactly the contrary is observed in Plentzia (Fig. 3). The MET values of mussels collected in Lekeitio do not differ significantly between tide levels.

Table IV illustrates the statistical signification of seasonal and zonal changes for each studied site. The MET of mussels collected in Galea, Zierbena and Lekeitio changes significantly with the season but not with tidal zonation itself. However, ANOVA indicates a significant interaction between both factors in Galea and Zierbena since MET values are not always lower at high tide level than at low one (Fig. 3). The MET values recorded in Plentzia do not only depend

on the season but also on the tide level (Table IV). Here, highest MET values are always recorded at low tide level (Fig. 3).

The statistical signification of the variability in MET observed between seasons and sites at different zonations on the shore is shown in Table V. According to the ANOVA tests, the MET values recorded in both high and low tide levels are significantly dissimilar between seasons and between sites.

DISCUSSION

In order to explain the widespread occurrence of necrotic tubules in September some considerations should be made. First, the highest annual temperature of the coastal waters in the Basque coast is reached in this month (unpublished data). HENRY (1987) reports the presence of necrotic tubules in clams, *Ruditapes decussatus*, exposed to high temperatures (26°C). In addition, high temperatures may induce spawning in bivalves (PURCHON, 1977) and hence may lead to a weakening which would increase their susceptibility to pathogens. Presently, we have observed different stages of gametogenesis in March and August and a post-spawning degenerative stage in the gonad of mussels collected in September. Such degenerative stage of the gonad tissue has been

Figure 3. Means and standar deviations (vertical lines) of MET values recorded in September 1987 (S), March 1988 (M) and August 1988 (A) in Galea (G), Zierbena (Z), Lekeitio (L) and Plentzia (P) at low (LT) and high (HT) tide levels.

Figura 3. Medias y desviaciones standard (líneas verticales) de valores de MET; datos de septiembre de 1987 (S), marzo de 1988 (M) y agosto de 1988 (A) en Galea (G), Zierbena (Z), Lekeitio (L) y Plentzia (P) en bajamar (LT) y pleamar (HT).

Table III. Two-way ANOVA carried out to assess the effects of pollution and natural stress (geographical site) and of tidal zonation on MET values at each season.

Tabla III. ANOVA de dos vías, ejecutado para determinar el efecto de la contaminación, del stress natural (localización geográfica) y de la zonación mareal en el MET en cada estación del año.

Season	Variation source	d.f.	F ratio
September	site (S)	3	0.465
	zonation (Z)	1	2.391
	interaction (SxZ)	3	3.608 *
	residual	1060	
	total	1067	
March	site	3	16.344 **
	zonation	1	18.946 **
	interaction	3	10.868 **
	residual	960	
	total	967	
August	site	3	41.927 **
	zonation	1	16.064 **
	interaction	3	5.829 *
	residual	952	
	total	959	

*: P< 0.05; **: P< 0.01

Table IV. Two-way ANOVA carried out to assess the effects of season and of tidal zonation on MET values at each geographical site.

Tabla IV. ANOVA de dos vías, que muestra el efecto de la estación y del nivel mareal en el MET para los distintos puntos de muestreo.

Site	Variation source	d.f.	F ratio
Galea	season	2	27.871 **
	zonation	1	0.364
	interaction	2	10.907 **
	residual	726	
	total	731	
Zierbena	season	2	70.139 **
	zonation	1	0.502
	interaction	2	5.732 **
	residual	726	
	total	731	
Lekeitio	season	2	25.522 **
	zonation	1	0.154
	interaction	2	2.648
	residual	742	
	total	747	
Plentzia	season	2	58.925 **
	zonation	1	29.169 **
	interaction	2	4.217 *
	residual	742	
	total	747	

*: P< 0.05; **: P< 0.01

Table V. Two-way ANOVA carried out to compare sites and seasons at each tide level. Based on MET values.

Tabla V. ANOVA de dos vías; muestra la comparación entre localidades y estaciones del año para cada nivel mareal. Basado en niveles del MET.

Tidal zonation	Variation source	d.f.	F ratio
Low Tide Level	site	3	17.497 **
	season	2	59.871 **
	interaction	6	6.516 **
	residual	1475	
	total	1486	
High Tide Level	site	3	3.850 **
	season	2	106.283 **
	interaction	6	9.450 **
	residual	1497	
	total	1508	

** : P< 0.01

related to a weakening of the general condition of molluscs (CAJARAVILLE, MARIGÓMEZ AND ANGULO, 1990; MARIGÓMEZ *ET AL.*, 1990). Seasonal trends in the prevalence of certain diseases have been elsewhere related to the end of the reproductive cycle (COUCH, 1984; BROUSSEAU, 1987; MARIGÓMEZ *ET AL.*, 1992; 1993).

CAJARAVILLE AND ANGULO (1991) have recently investigated the nature of the necrotic condition of the digestive tubules of mussels collected from the Basque Coast and suggests that an Iridoviridae virus might be responsible for this anomalous morphology of the digestive tubules. Moreover, this author reports increased prevalences of the necrotic condition after long periods of maintenance in the laboratory. RASMUSSEN (1986) has described the seasonality of viral infections in *Mytilus edulis* and concluded that maximum peak values for the prevalence of these diseases occur in September. In summary, necrotic tubules might be the consequence of a seasonal infectious disease but, however, this aspect deserves further research previous to obtain any feasible explanation.

Accordingly, very low MET values have been recorded in September if compared with the remainder samples. Thus, differences between sites and tidal zones appear to be buffered at this season. The combined effect of reproductive stress (PURCHON, 1977), increased temperature (HENRY, 1987) and seasonal infectiousness (high occurrence of necrotic tubules) might account for the observed homogeneous morphology of the digestive tubules of mussels belonging to different sites and tidal levels. However, the picture is quite different in the other two sampling times where different degrees of pollution and environmental factors are expressed in different MET values.

The digestive gland of mussels collected from *Plentzia* exhibits a structure which agrees with the theoretical pattern which is featured by low MET values at HT zone and high MET values at LT zone (ROBINSON *ET AL.*, 1981; MARIGÓMEZ *ET AL.* 1990). This pattern is

modified in the other three sampling sites for various different reasons.

Pollution is the first one (LOWE *ET AL.*, 1981; COUCH, 1984; VEGA *ET AL.*, 1989; CAJARAVILLE *ET AL.*, 1992). Mussels from Galea and Zierbena present an inverted picture since MET values recorded at LT zone were lower than those recorded at HT zone. The fact of being polluted sites might account for these findings since shorter aerial exposure mean longer exposure to water pollutants and, in addition, the water which baths mussels inhabiting HT zone comes from the sea and is expected to be cleaner than water coming from the industrialized areas along the river and at the rivermouth.

A second reason is the natural roughness of the environment. Strong wave-beating may force mussels from Lekeitio to spend an extra amount of energy in keeping themselves fixed to the substrate by producing more byssus. In addition, if the nutrient levels are not high enough to support this extra demand, this may result in the malnutrition of mussels. As a result, the digestive gland resembles the picture of starved or stressed molluscs (LOWE *ET AL.*, 1981; MARIGÓMEZ *ET AL.*, 1990; 1993; CAJARAVILLE *ET AL.*, 1991, 1992) and, consequently, the effect of tidal zonation is masked and MET values are equally low at both tide levels.

It can be concluded that the changes in the digestive gland structure of mussels may be indicative of environmental stress due to pollution but, however, we should be cautious since some natural factors may interfere and produce similar effects. For this reason, the accurate selection of sites and the systemic record of variables indicative of changes in natural factors are highly recommended to plan effective monitoring programmes based on feasible measures of environmental stress on biological samples. Moreover, although the present work has been focused on the study of a particular index at a single biological effect, we are aware that any attempt to develop environmental monitoring programmes should be multidisciplinary.

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